

Spectrophotometric determination of rhodium(III) using 5-Br-PADAP and *N*-hydroxy-*N,N'*-diphenylbenzamidine as reagent by extracting it in dichloromethane

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A rapid and sensitive spectrophotometric method for the determination of Rh^{III} with 2-[(5-bromo-2-pyridylazo)]-5-diethylaminophenol (5-Br-PADAP) is described. The Rh^{III} -2-[(5-bromo-2-pyridylazo)]-5-diethylaminophenol (5-Br-PADAP) complex is extracted with *N*-hydroxy-*N,N'*-diphenylbenzamidine (HDPBA) in dichloromethane at pH range 5.8–6.5 to give a red coloured complex. The extracted complex shows λ_{max} at 460 nm. The reproducibility of the method is checked by finding relative standard deviation value (RSD, $n = 10$) for solution containing $1 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ Rh^{III} , and the RSD value of the method is found to be 1.7%. The system obeyed Beer's law up to $0.6 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of rhodium and the detection limit of the method is 32 ng ml^{-1} on a three times the standard deviation of the blank absorbance basis. The Sandell's sensitivity and molar absorptivity of the complex are $0.00036 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ and $2.8 \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively. The effect of foreign ions and other experimental variables are studied. Rh^{III} has been successfully determined in automobile exhaust sample, soil and vegetation samples.

The analysis of platinum group metals in environmental sample is a difficult task due to their low concentration and interference and also the techniques are quite expensive and require costly maintenance and skilled hands for operation. Cathodic Stripping Voltammetry is the most sensitive technique but suffers from matrix interference. Large number of reagents, such as 2-thiobarbaturic acid in water¹, 1-phenyl-3-thiobenzoylthiocarbamide², *N,N'*-dipyridylthiourea³, rhodamine 6G4, 2-(5-bromo-2-pyridylazo)-5-(*N*-propyl-*N*-sulphoprolamino)phenol⁵, buta-perazine dimaleinate⁶ and 2-[(5-bromo-2-pyridylazo)]-5-diethylaminophenol⁷ are reported for spectrophotometric determination of rhodium. These methods, however, are not suitable due to the tedium involved in the methods, e.g. critical pH ranges, poor sensitivity and problem of matrix interference. The present paper deals with a simple and highly sensitive ($\epsilon = 2.8 \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) spectrophotometric method for the determination of rhodium in automobile exhaust samples, using 2-[(5-bromo-2-pyridylazo)]-5-diethylaminophenol (5-Br-PADAP) in presence of ascorbic acid, ethylene glycol, Brij-35 and *N*-hydroxy-*N,N'*-diphenylbenzamidine (HDPBA). The characteristic features of some spectrophotometric methods reported earlier for determining rhodium(III) are presented in Table 1.

Results and discussion

The determination of Rh^{III} has been done by the extrac-

tion of Rh^{III} -5-Br-PADAP-(Brij-35)-HDPBA complex into dichloromethane at pH 6.0. The experimental condition for the determination of Rh^{III} by present method has been summarized in Table 2. The extracted complex of Rh^{III} -5-Br-PADAP-(Brij-35)-HDPBA in dichloromethane, exhibits maximum absorbance at 460 nm against the reagent blank, at pH 6.0. The effect of several organic solvents on the formation and extraction of Rh^{III} -5-Br-PADAP-(Brij-35)-HDPBA complex has been studied. The values of molar absorptivity at wavelength of maximum absorption of the complex in various solvents are as follows : benzene (ϵ , $1.0 \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$; λ_{max} 640 nm), ethyl acetate (ϵ , $8.5 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$; λ_{max} 480 nm), iso-butyl methyl ketone (ϵ , $8.5 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$; λ_{max} 460 nm), xylene (ϵ , $1.9 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$; λ_{max} 520 nm), chloroform (ϵ , $2.8 \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$; λ_{max} 460 nm), dichloromethane (ϵ , $2.8 \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$; λ_{max} 460 nm). Complete extraction (>99%) and maximum absorbance of the complex is observed with dichloromethane as compared with other solvents. Since dichloromethane is less toxic than the chloroform, it was chosen as solvent for present work.

The maximum absorption of the Rh complex at different pH values were plotted and all the curves were found to be similar in nature and exhibited maximum absorption at 460 nm in the pH range 5.8–6.5. The experiment was carried out at $\text{pH } 6.0 \pm 0.2$ using buffer.

Table 1. Comparison of spectrophotometric reagents for the determination of rhodium(III)

Reagents	Range of concentration $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	$\epsilon = \text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ $\lambda_{\text{max}} \text{ (nm)}$	Sandell's sensitivity*/ detection limit**, (* = $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, ** = ng ml^{-1})	Heating time
2-Thiobarbaritic acid ^a in water	0.24–14	$1.04 \times 10^4/327$	0.0098*	60 min at 75°C
<i>N,N'</i> -Dipyridyl thiourea ^b	0.60–3.56	$1.5 \times 10^4/327$	0.0095*	Heat upto boiling 30–35 min
1-Phenyl-3- thiobenzoylthio- carbamide ^c	Upto 5	$3.1 \times 10^4/325$	0.0033*	Extraction with organic solution
Rhodamine 6G ^d	0.5–5	$1.3 \times 10^5/565$	–	80°C and above
2-(5-Bromo-2- pyridylazo)-5-(<i>N</i> - propyl- <i>N</i> -sulpho- prolamino)-phenol ^e	0.04–0.8	$1.09 \times 10^5/600$	–	20 min at 95°C
Butaperazine dimaleinate ^f	0.2–28	$2.44 \times 10^3/465$	0.042*	20 min at 20–50°C
2-[(5-Bromo-2- pyridylazo)]-5- diethylaminophenol ^g	0.03–2.5	$2.54 \times 10^5/606$	72**	60 min
2-[(5-Bromo-2- pyridylazo)]-5- diethylaminophenol + TX-100 + <i>N</i> -hydroxy- <i>N,N'</i> - diphenylbenzamidine	0.04–0.6	$2.8 \times 10^5/460$	32**	40 min

^aRef. 1, ^bRef. 3, ^cRef. 2, ^dRef. 4, ^eRef. 5, ^fRef. 6, ^gRef. 7.

During the systematic investigation of the colour reaction, it was observed that the complex formed initially after heating rhodium with 5-Br-PADAP, ascorbic acid, ethylene glycol and Brij-35 solution, which produced a red coloration after extraction with HDPBA, whereas the one that was formed in cold solution reacted slowly, the colour development being incomplete even after standing for 1 h at room temperature. The formation of rhodium^{III}-5-Br-PADAP complex is accelerated by heating on water bath at 90°C. The absorbance of the complex abruptly increased after heating for 30 min and maximum absorbance obtained after 60 min. After 90 min the absorbance of Rh^{III}-5-Br-PADAP complex started decreasing. A heating time of 40 min was adopted as 99% of the maximum absorbance is obtained after this time. The Rh^{III}-5-Br-PADAP complex once formed is stable and gives a constant absorbance for 24 h. A 6.5×10^{-4} mol/L solution of ascorbic acid was employed through out the experiment for complete colour development of complex.

The studies on effect of concentration of Brij-35 indicate that a concentration range of $(7.5-10.8) \times 10^{-6}$ mol/L was sufficient for maximum color development of Rh^{III}-5-

Br-PADAP-(Brij-35)-HDPBA complex. Therefore, 8.3×10^{-6} mol/L Brij-35 was kept constant through out the experiment. Fig. 1 shows the optimum reagent concentration ranges of 5-Br-PADAP, Brij-35 and HDPBA.

Table 2. Experimental conditions for the determination of rhodium(III) with 5-Br-PADAP

pH range	5.8–6.5
Methanol solution of 5-Br-PADAP	2.9×10^{-4} M (0.01%)
Buffer solution	pH 6.0
Surfactant solution	8.34×10^{-4} M (0.1%, w/v) of Brij-35
Maximum of complex absorption	460 nm
Fulfilment of Beer's law	Upto 0.6 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$
Molar absorptivity	$2.8 \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ RSD = 1.7%; CL ^α = $(2.76-2.84) \times 10^5$
Stability of complex	>24 h

RSD = Estimated relative standard deviation for $n = 6$.
α = Corresponds 95% confidence, CL = confidence limit.

Several water-soluble organic solvents such as ethylene glycol, dioxane, dimethylformamide and glycerin were added in aqueous solution to promote the formation of Rh^{III}-5-Br-PADAP-(Brij-35)-HDPBA complex. Ethylene glycol and glycerin imparted similar colour reaction with identical value of molar absorptivity (ϵ , $2.8 \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$

cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} 460 nm), as compared to other organic solvents which showed comparatively less sensitivity of the Rh^{III} complex. Consequently, an ethylene glycol content of 10% v/v (1.60 mol/L) was used. It was observed that at a concentration range $(2.8\text{--}5.6) \times 10^{-2}$ mol/L of ethylene glycol in aqueous phase was required for the maximum colour development of Rh^{III} -5-Br-PADAP-(Brij-35)-HDPBA complex. Therefore, 3.2×10^{-2} mol/L ethylene glycol was kept constant throughout the experiment. The present investigation was carried out at 2.9×10^{-5} mol/L of 5-Br-PADAP throughout the experiment as in this concentration maximum and stable absorbance is obtained. A 1.7×10^{-3} mol/L HDPBA was employed throughout the experiment for complete extraction of rhodium(III) complex.

Table 3. Tolerance limit of diverse ion in the determination of $1 \mu\text{g Rh}^{\text{III}}$ /10 ml at pH 6.0 ± 0.2

Ions added	Tolerance limit* mg 10 ml^{-1}
	Organic phase
$\text{Pt}^{\text{IV}}, \text{Pd}^{\text{II}}$	0.040 ^a
Zn^{II}	0.093 ^b
Co^{II}	0.12
$\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$	0.15 ^c
$\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}, \text{Mn}^{\text{II}}$	0.20
V	0.40 ^c
$\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}, \text{Cd}^{\text{II}}$	0.50
$\text{Zr}^{\text{IV}}, \text{Hg}^{\text{II}}$	1.0
Pb^{II}	2.0
W^{VI}	20
Sr^{II}	80
Mg^{II}	160
Thiocyanate	0.50
Bromide	2.0
Iodide	2.5
Fluoride	2.7
Oxalate	20
EDTA	30
Citrate	50
Tartrate	250

a = Masked by 3 ml of 0.1% (w/v) KSCN solution.

b = Masked by 0.6 ml of 0.1% (v/v) glycerol.

c = Masked by 3 ml of 0.1% (w/v) EDTA solution.

* Ions were considered to interference when they caused a change in the absorbance of the Rh^{III} -{5-Br-PADAP}-{Brij-35}-HDPBA complex ($A = 0.278$) by $\geq \pm 2\%$.

The composition of the rhodium complex was determined by the curve fitting method. The molar ratio of metal to 5-Br-PADAP, Brij-35 and HDPBA was determined by plotting logarithmic value of distribution ratio of metal [$\log \{A_{\text{eq}}/A_{\text{max}} - A_{\text{eq}}\}$] (where, A_{max} = maximum absorbance of the complex at λ_{max} under optimum reagent concentration at a level of $1 \mu\text{g Rh}^{\text{III}}$ 10 ml^{-1} organic phase and A_{eq} = absorbance of Rh^{III} complex at equilibration with different known concentrations of reagents viz. 5-Br-PADAP/Brij-35/HDPBA) versus logarithmic values of varied known concentrations of 5-Br-PADAP/Brij-35/HDPBA in dichloromethane.

The inclinations of the curves for 5-Br-PADAP, Brij-35 and HDPBA were found to be close to integer 3, 3 and 2, respectively. Thus, a 1 : 3 : 3 : 2 molar ratio complex of Rh^{III} : 5-Br-PADAP : Brij-35 : HDPBA in dichloromethane was predicted. Fig. 2 indicates the metal-ligand ratio of the 5-Br-PADAP, Brij-35 and HDPBA.

Subscript 0 indicates organic phase i.e. dichloromethane.

The system obeyed Beer's law up to $0.6 \mu\text{g Rh}^{\text{III}} \text{ ml}^{-1}$ with an excellent linearity in terms of correlation coefficient value of 0.997. The sensitivity of the Rh^{III} -5-Br-PADAP-(TX-100)-HDPBA complex, calculated in terms of molar absorptivity is $2.8 \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$; λ_{max} , 460 nm. The precision of the method in terms of relative stan-

Fig. 1. Effect of reagent concentration on the formation of Rh^{III} -{5-Br-PADAP}-{Brij-35}-HDPBA complex in dichloromethane; a = Brij-35, b = 5-Br-PADAP, c = HDPBA.

Fig. 2. Plot of curve fitting data for the determination of stoichiometry of the Rh^{III} -{5-Br-PADAP}-{Brij-35}-HDPBA complex in dichloromethane; a = Brij-35, b = 5-Br-PADAP, c = HDPBA.

dard deviation ($n = 10$) for the determination of $1.0 \mu\text{g Rh}^{\text{III}}$ is 1.7%. In this method the detection limit, defined as for photometry, the concentration of analyte causing more absorbance than thrice the standard deviation of ten replicate measurements of blank absorbance at 95% probability is $32 \text{ ng Rh}^{\text{III}} \text{ ml}^{-1}$ in organic phase.

The interference of platinum group metals and several cations and anions was observed, at 460 nm, with samples containing $1.0 \mu\text{g Rh}^{\text{III}}$. Substances tested and tolerance is listed in Table 3.

Table 4 Determination of rhodium in the auto exhaust, soil and vegetation samples

Samples	Rhodium added to the sample $\mu\text{g/ml}$	Rhodium found by			
		Present method		Reported method (10)	
		Concentration of Rh^{III} $\mu\text{g-Rh}^{\text{a}}$	RSD* $\pm\%$	Concentration of Rh^{III} $\mu\text{g-Rh}^{\text{a}}$	RSD* $\pm\%$
Sample A					
A ₁	1.0	1.040	1.7	1.045	1.2
A ₂	1.0	1.050	2.0	1.049	1.9
A ₃	1.0	1.067	1.9	1.066	2.0
A ₄	1.0	1.061	2.5	1.066	2.5
Sample B					
B ₁	1.5	1.525	2.5	1.520	1.8
B ₂	1.5	1.570	2.3	1.576	1.9
B ₃	1.5	1.520	2.0	1.510	2.1
B ₄	1.5	1.500	1.9	1.400	1.8
Sample C					
C ₁	1.5	1.530	2.6	1.528	1.9
C ₂	1.5	1.500	2.0	1.500	2.4
C ₃	1.5	1.410	2.1	1.500	2.0
C ₄	1.5	1.544	1.9	1.560	1.8

^a $\mu\text{g-Rh}^{\text{III}}$ in exhaust sampling at a fuel burning rate of 10 km L^{-1} for 3 h

A₁, A₂, A₃ and A₄ are the automobile exhaust samples collected from 4 different Indian four-wheeler equipped with catalytic converters

B₁, B₂, B₃ and B₄ are the road side dust and soil samples collected from national highways

C₁, C₂, C₃ and C₄ are the vegetation samples collected from roadside plant

* Four analysis were carried out

Experimental

A Carl-Zeiss Jena (Jena, Germany) spectrophotometer fitted with EK-5 unit and matched quartz cells of 1 cm path length was used for all absorbance measurements. A Systronic digital pH meter type 335 was employed for the measurement of pH.

All chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade, B.D.H./E. Merck/Glaxo/SD fine Chem. The stock solution of rhodium(III) was prepared by dissolving 0.140 g of rhodium(III) nitrate in 100 ml of 1 mol/L hydrochloric acid. *N*-Hydroxy-*N,N'*-diphenylbenzamide (HDPBA) was synthesized as according to the literature⁸. A 3.5×10^{-3} mol/L (0.1%, w/v) solution of HDPBA in dichloromethane were taken for extraction. A 2.9×10^{-4} mol/L (0.01%) 5-Br-PADAP solution in methanol was employed for colour development. A 0.14% (w/v), (7.9×10^{-3} mol/L) of ascorbic acid in distilled water was used. 0.1% (w/v), (8.34×10^{-4} mol/L) of Brij-35 in distilled water was used. A 10% (1.61 mol/L) of ethylene glycol in distilled water was used. $\text{KHC}_8\text{H}_4\text{O}_4\text{-NaOH}$ buffer solution of pH 6.0 was used for pH adjustment⁹.

Procedure for the determination of rhodium : An aliquot of the standard solution containing $1.0 \mu\text{g Rh}^{\text{III}}$ was taken in a 125 ml separatory funnel. To the above solution mix 0.8 ml of ascorbic acid, 0.1 ml of Brij-35, 0.2 ml of eth-

ylene glycol and 1 ml of 5-Br-PADAP. Adjust the pH of the aqueous phase at 6.0 ± 0.2 with buffer solution in a total volume of 7 ml; keep it on a boiling water bath for 50 min at 90°C , cool the content and extract it with 2×2 ml of HDPBA in dichloromethane. Combine the extract and dry over anhydrous sodium sulphate (2 g). Make up the organic phase with dichloromethane in 10 ml volumetric flask. Measure the absorbance of the complex against reagent blank at λ_{max} 460 nm.

Application of the method : The method has been satisfactorily applied for the determination of Rh^{III} in automobile engine exhaust samples, soil and vegetation in samples collected from national highway. The actual contents of the Rh^{III} in automobile exhaust samples were determined with the help of the calibration curve. The Rh^{III} concentrations in various car (having catalytic converters) exhaust samples and soil samples from national highway have been incorporated in Table 4. The comparison of the results indicates good correlation between the proposed procedure and other reported methods.

The reagent 2-[(5-bromo-2-pyridylazo)]-5-diethylamino-phenol (5-Br-PADAP) provides a new, sensitive and accurate method for the spectrophotometric determination of rhodium(III). The reagent has the advantages of high sensitivity, selectively and easy availability. Table 1 shows a

comparison with the other colorimetric methods for rhodium(III), and it was found that 5-Br-PADAP method is more sensitive and simple than many other sensitive methods and are better in lower concentration ranges as compared to other reagents and methods. The proposed method has been applied successfully for the determination of rhodium in automobile exhaust sample, soil and vegetation samples.

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